

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DERIVATIVES AND WORD FORMATION METHODS (STRUCTURAL ASPECT OF WORD FORMATION DESIGNATIONS)

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Abstract

Our article is about derived words and the ways of word formation underlying the structural aspect of word-formation markup. We also give arguments that all derived words created with the help of word-formation techniques are the result of the word-formation process.

Keywords: word-formation markup, derived words, ways of word formation.

Word formation is a separate branch of linguistics. In Kazakh linguistics, word formation began to be studied as a separate branch only in the 80-90s of the XX century, first as part of morphology, some problems were considered in lexicology. The collection "the system of Word formation of the modern Kazakh language", published in 1989, was recognized as an independent branch of Word formation and became the basis for the formation of theoretical problems [1]. And in the academic "Kazakh grammar", published in 2002, the field of Word formation was given as a large chapter and found its place [2].

In Kazakh linguistics, word formation is studied from a descriptive (synchronous) and historical (diachronic) aspect. The works of Kazakh scientists have contributed to the formation of Word formation as a separate branch. In particular, N. Oralbayeva, G. Kaliyev, S. Isaev, A. Salkynbay, Z. Beisembayeva, L. Zhanalina, B. Kassym, G. Shaharman, G. Zheksembayeva, zh. Otarbekova, A. Ibatov, E. Zhanpeisov and others.

Word formation studies the function of language to create a name, to create a new word, to give birth to a word.

The main object of study of the word-forming branch of the language are derived words. Derived words are lexical units formed by word-building methods of the language. Derivative words are the result of the word-forming activity of the language.

Since new things and new concepts are continuous, the emergence of new names through word formation is also a continuous phenomenon.

The composition of derived words consists of one main, one auxiliary morpheme, or consists of two main morphemes. The composition of these examples is

made up of the main and auxiliary morphemes. The composition of derived words is made up of two main morphemes. If the first auxiliary morpheme is connected, the derived Root is formed, and in the second case, complex words are formed.

A derivative word contains an independent meaningful word, which is the basis for its creation. The meaning of the word that was the basis in the derived word becomes the core to the meaning of the derived word. For example: medicine doctor, treatment Polyclinic, lecture lecture, retirement pensioner, etc. For example, if we take the derivative word mentor, then the word mentor in its composition was based on the lexical meaning of the derivative word mentor. And the creator of the derived word added The Meaning of the profession to the main word of the second morpheme-gertalim. Thus, the word mentor was created, which means educator. That is, the meaning of the word mentor derivative is formed from the meaning of the morphemes teach and-Ger. Therefore, the meaning of this derivative word is associated with the meaning of the word teaching in its composition. Such a semantic connection is also clearly visible in the complex word-forming adverbs. For example, the word greenhouse is made up of two words. One is warm, the other is just. This word formed the name of the warm place where the plant is grown by combining the Word "year", which is a sign of a thing, and the simple word "place", which means "place". In other words, the meaning of the complex word greenhouse is formed from the meaning of SYN in the composition. Therefore, a word that does not have a semantic connection cannot be a derived word.

The basis in the composition of the meaning of derivative words will be more complex than the

meaning of the word. That is, the meaning of the base word and the meaning of the derivative word are not equal. Because in derived words, the meaning of the base word is added to the meaning of the suffix attached to them. The base in the composition of the derived root combines the meaning of the word and the meaning of the word-forming suffix to create the meaning of the derived Root [3].

From the word that served as the basis for the formation of the derivative word, the composition of the derivative word will also be more complex. For example: *әкім әкімшілік, жекеше жекешелендіру, шебер шеберхана, мейрам мейрамхана* etc. From the first of these, the composition of the second is complex, the first consists of one morpheme, the second of two morphemes. It is a strict pattern in the language that the composition of derived words is more complex than the composition of the main word. However, not only derived words formed by the semantic approach in the language are subject to this pattern. Since there is no personal change in the composition of words formed by the semantic approach, that is, the derived word is created by acquiring a new meaning, the composition will be the same as the base word. For example, the word *құн* as a term in economic science is a derivative word, that is, it has another meaning in addition to its previous meaning, but there is no change in personality.

In terms of the formation of derivative words from two morphemes, they are similar to other two-morpheme linguistic phenomena in the language. For example, the word differentiation, i.e. form composition units also consist of two or more morphemes. However, while auxiliary morphemes in the composition of derivative words give rise to a new word and create a lexical unit with a new meaning, the second base only adds an additional grammatical meaning without changing the lexical meaning of the word, the base gives rise to the grammatical form of the word, that is, it does not create an independent lexeme with a new meaning.

If a word has only one lexical meaning in a different person (in a word-forming paradigm), then in a word-forming paradigm there are as many lexical meanings as there are members of it, and accordingly there are as many independent lexical units. For example, *білім, білгіш, білгір* are root words formed from one root, each of which is an independent lexeme, *адамға, адамды, адамда* etc the paradigm of words is a grammatical transformation of a word with only one lexical meaning.

Similarly, complex words formed by a combination, which is one of the derived words, belong to a phenomenon similar in personality to a phrase. However, complex words carry a single lexical meaning, no matter how many syllables they consist of. And all the consonants contained in a phrase are collected and do not carry a single lexical meaning, as in complex words, they do not form a single name. Each word in the composition of a phrase is a separate sentence-forming member, a separate independent meaningful word. And no matter how many consonants a compound word contains, it will be only one member of the sentence. For example, in the sentence *Қызыл*

ала көйлегі өзіне жарасып тұр, қызыл ала the answer to the question of what is the compound adjective "what?" is only one determinative member of the sentence.

Derivative words, like root words in a language, are the names of objects and their signs in real life, and therefore belong to a lexical unit and are included in the vocabulary of the language, enriching it. Since derivative words are ready-made lexical units that are created and entered into the vocabulary at each stage, they are used ready-made in a sentence, as well as basic root words, that is, derivatives are lexical units that are obtained ready-made for any sentence, regardless of the construction of the sentence.

Derivative words are divided into the following two groups depending on their composition:

- A) Derived roots;
- B) Complex words.

Derived roots 1) the derived Root is a two-morpheme word, they are: the base word and the word-forming suffix; 2) the meaning of the derived Root is formed from the meaning of the base word and the word-forming suffix in its composition; 3) the base word and the meaning of the derived root in the composition of the derived Root are related.

Since derived roots are recognized according to the current stage of development of the language, the division of morphemes in their composition is clearly visible. For example: *кедей +лік, қымыз + хана, тап + қыр, тот + ық*, etc. all the derived roots clearly show the morphemes in their composition. However, this situation does not apply to derived roots in a historical context. Because the morphemes contained in historical derived roots have been destroyed. Therefore, they are not currently considered a derived root.

Word formation approaches:

Derivative words are not formed randomly, as it should be. It is formed according to the word-forming laws of the language, that is, through ready-made word-forming patterns in the language. For example, derived roots are most often formed by the main root + word-forming suffix pattern: *мал + шы, қой + шы, егін + ші*, etc. the main morpheme in these words is a noun, and the suffix *-шы/ші* adds the value of the business owner to the attached Word, creating a new meaningful word. Also, this suffix permanently attaches this meaning to the word to which it is attached. In other words, a derived word has a consistently formed way, way, pattern (model), meaning, adverbial meaning.

Derivative words are formed in the language in different ways. The word formation system of the Kazakh language has three main approaches that have been used since ancient times. They are: *synthetic, analytical, lexico-semantic*.

Synthetic approach.

Since the Kazakh language is an agglutinative language, the derivative word-maker is the main approach. The creation of a derivative word through a synthetic approach has its own specifics, which is formed in the language. To create a derived word through this approach, two Language units must be involved in it:

- 1) lexically meaningful word;
- 2) word formation suffix.

Each of these linguistic units involved in the creation of a derived word through a synthetic approach has its own function.

The lexical unit in the composition of the derived word is based on the meaning of the derived word. It is called the base word [4]. A base word is a lexically meaningful word that is the basis for creating a derivative word. For example, *дәрігер, аңшы, өнерпаз* base words in derivative words: *дәрі, аң, өнер* words. The meaning of derivative words and the meaning of the base words in their composition are constantly related. This applies not only to derived roots, that is, words formed using a synthetic approach, it is an established, strictly observed pattern in relation to word formation in general. Thus, in the composition of derived roots, the base is the function of the word itself to carry a new lexical meaning, to be the core.

The connectedness of the meaning of the derived root word and the base word is especially evident in the word-forming nest. No matter how many derived roots are in each word-forming cell, they will be semantically related to each other. Because of the composition of all derived roots in one nest, the base word of the nest is formed, and the derivative roots in the nest are related in meaning. For example: *бастық, басшы, басқар, басқарма, баспана, басшылық, баста, бастама* etc. The common basis for all these derived words is that the word "head" connects the meanings of all of them.

The second person, the second linguistic unit in the synthetic approach is the word-forming suffix. In synthetic word formation, the suffix is considered the main unit, without its participation, no derived Root is formed using a synthetic approach.

Derived words formed using a synthetic approach are called derived roots. The derived root base is formed by adding a word-forming suffix to the word. For example, *байпақ+шаң, сыр+лы, шүкір+лік, әсем+паз* etc.

Each of the morphemes contained in derived roots, created using a synthetic approach, has a place. The main morpheme is in the first place, the auxiliary morpheme, that is, the word-forming suffix, is in the second place, that is, the base stands at the end of the word. The place of morphemes in the composition of derived roots is constant. Deviations from this pattern are found only in some morphemes entered from another language. For example, *бисаясат, бейкүнә* etc.

A word-forming suffix has a function that creates a derived root. Its main function is to create a derivative lexical meaning. Most word-forming suffixes create a lexical new meaning. For example, *ойыншық* the suffix *-шық*, which created the root of the derivative, has a lexical meaning other than the word game base, that is, it is necessary for the game, created the name of the object being *ойын*. Сонда мұндағы *ойын* сөзінің лексикалық мағынасы мен *ойыншық* туынды түбірінің лексикалық мағынасы екі басқа. Then the lexical meaning of the word *ойын* here and the lexical meaning of the root of the *ойыншық* are two other.

Each of the word-forming suffixes, along with its own specific meaning, has common meanings that are common to several of them. For example, a number of suffixes create words denoting a material concept, a number of suffixes give rise to words denoting a criticism, quality, sign of an object, and now a group of derived root verbs, for example, *-сыз/ сіз, -лы/лі, -шаң/шең, -ғыш/гіш* suffixes such as quality value if derived roots, *-ла/ле, -ғыла/гіле, -ар/ер* suffixes such as action-valued derivative root verbs create. Suffixes with such common meanings are formed as suffixes of a certain class of words. Therefore, when the question of word-forming suffixes is raised, it is customary to consider them individually as a word-formation of each word class. This tradition is also characteristic of the periods when word formation is considered as part of morphology. For example, noun-generating suffixes, verb-generating suffixes, etc.

Analytical approach.

The analytical approach is a productive approach that came from ancient times in our language, which supplemented our language with many complex words. The analytical approach to word formation differs from the synthetic approach by its word formation units. If in the synthetic approach a lexical unit and a word-forming suffix are involved in the creation of a derivative word, in the analytical approach a suffix is not involved, where only two or more lexical units act as a word-forming person.

In an analytical approach, two or more words are combined with each other *бірігу (кірігу), тіркесу, қосарлану, қысқару* a new lexically meaningful word is created.

The combination of the analytical approach, that is, the word combination type, creates lexical units in the Kazakh language, in which two or more words are pronounced with one accent, combined into a single sound composition and carrying a single lexical meaning. For example, *қырықбуын, аққу, итмұрын* etc.

Wordthe method of incorporation can be divided into two ways of unification, integration. Each of the inner consonants of words formed by the method of union fully retains its own sound composition: *қолбасы, таусағыз, бойтұмар, көлбақа, көртышқан* etc. But the independent meanings of the words are not preserved, but carry a single lexical meaning. And the sound composition of words formed by the method of integration, when used independently, is not preserved, they are transferred to a single sound composition. For example, *білезік (білек жүзік), апар (алып бар), табалдырық (табан тұрық), қайны (қайын іні)* etc. The word compound type of analytical approach to word formation is a very productive approach to creating derivative words in a language.

The duality approach is the way in which two words merge into one, creating a single meaningful word. Words formed by the double way are called double words. It belongs to the ancient method used in the language of the most ancient written monuments. Our language is very rich in double words. For example, *ата-ана, туған-туысқан, көрпе-жастық, өнер-білім, ән-күй, дәрі-дәрмек* etc.

The duality approach has its own pattern formed in the language. Double words formed by the method of duplication, firstly, must be from the same word class. For example, *бау-бақша, қыз-келіншек, аяқ-табақ, үлгі-өнеге* etc. Secondly, double words formed by the duality method are often synonymous. For example, *сән-салтанат, сауыт-сайман, ойын-күлкі, туган-туыс* etc.

The attachment type of the analytical approach is also one of the very productive ones. Compound words formed by combination are formed by the combination of two independent words. Their sentences are written separately from each other, but their sentences have lost their independence of meaning and have a single meaning. For example, *қызыл ала* the thing is one color in its own way, it is a color that is not homogeneous, but mixed with red another color. Same as *тоқпан жiлiк*, name of one of the types of shingles, *алтыс бес* the number is the name of a new single number, which is the sum of the numbers sixty and five, and the two words merge to form a single lexical meaning. However, the derived meaning in complex words does not go far from the meaning of the SYN, which serves to create them, but is closely related to them. It is formed from the sum of two meanings.

The abbreviation approach is especially necessary for the abbreviated use of complex names. For example, ҚазҰУ (Қазақ ұлттық университеті), АлМУ (Алматы мемлекеттік университеті), АҚШ (Америка құрама штаты), БАҚ (Бұқаралық ақпарат құралдары) etc. Such words are called abbreviated words.

Thus, words formed using an analytical approach are called compound words.

Complex words.

Kazakh is a language rich in complex words. Complex words contribute to the enrichment of our vocabulary from ancient times to this day. Compound words belong to derived words. They are created using an analytical approach to word formation.

Complex words refer to a complex problem that has not been fully solved in science, despite the fact that language naming is a very common phenomenon.

The main feature of complex words is that they have a complex structure, that is, they are formed from the sum of several lexical units. The similarity between a singular word and a compound word is that both belong to a lexical unit that has an independent lexical meaning. The difference is that a singular word contains only one lexical unit, while a compound word contains at least two lexical units. Complex words are formed from independent words with lexical meaning. For example, *алтыбақан, белбеу, бозторғай, ақсақал* etc. the fact that the composition of each of the complex words, such as, is made up of independent words, does not cause any controversy.

Lexical units in the composition of complex words create a derivative meaning in complex words. The meanings of complex words will be related to the meanings of the conjunctions that make it [5].

Complex words, despite the fact that they are formed from several words with independent lexical meanings, carry a single lexical meaning and,

accordingly, are recognized as a word with a single lexical meaning. No matter how many complex words consist of sounds, it is one word. Compound word pronouns do not form a single phrase in a sentence. The composition will be constant, it cannot be changed. For example, *аққұба, бозторғай* changing the composition of complex words, *құбаала, торғайбоз* if we, they are *аққұба, бозторғай* it cannot give the meanings of complex words. Because the meanings of complex words were integrated and had a single meaning. Therefore, both the composition of complex words and the order of their conjugation are constant.

Since the meaning of a complex word is integrated and conveys a single meaning, it is recognized as a single word and used in a ready-made form in a sentence. Therefore, since complex words are lexical units that are taken into a sentence in a ready-made form, it performs the function of one word in a sentence, has one member of the sentence, answers one question. A word is a word, a word is a word. No linguistic units are added between the consonants in the composition of complex words. The composition of complex words is also divided in pronunciation, and pauses are not pronounced between the syllables. The compound word is pronounced in a single Rhythm.

The above four types of analytical approach create four types of compound word, which are: *біріккен сөздер, қос сөздер, тіркесті сөздер, қысқарған сөздер*.

Compound words are words that have moved into a single lexical unit in terms of the meaning and sound composition of two, sometimes three words. Combined words differ from other complex words in that the word-forming units in their composition move into a single sound composition and merge, that is, they are written together, since the consonants of other types of complex words are written separately.

United words are words whose sounds are united both in meaning and in person, express a single Meaning, have a single sound composition, are pronounced with one accent and serve as one member of the sentence. For example, *әнұран, елорда, елбасы, елтаңба, әуежай* etc.

Integrated words are a word whose composition has undergone a sound change, which has now moved to a single sound composition, expresses a single lexical meaning, answers one question in a sentence, acts as one member of a sentence, is pronounced with one accent. For example, *әкел, әпер, биыл, бүгін, білезік* etc.

Double words.

Double words occupy a large place in the vocabulary of all Turkic languages and are among the most frequently used lexical units in the language. Double words are formed using the dual approach of the analytical approach. For example, *ойын-сауық, ине-жiп, ыдыс-аяқ, ата-ана, құрал-сайман, ұзынды-қысқалы* etc.

The composition of double words does not occur from any words. The language has its own established patterns of formation of double words. Both

conjunctions of double words come from the word of the same word class. For example, *жауын-шашын, тамыр-таныс, қауіп-қатер* etc. both conjunctions of double words are nouns. This also applies to other word classes.

Double words are formed from words that are close in meaning, with a certain semantic connection between them. No semantic connection, words that are not related to each other can merge with each other and form a double word. Double words are the result of two equal words close in meaning being doubled and transformed into a single word [6].

In modern language, double words sometimes have one ending, and sometimes both endings are meaningless. This is due to the current stage of development of the language, when they first became meaningful words, and then one, sometimes both, as a result of language development, the lexical meaning faded, or completely lost its meaning and reached the present degree. For example, *бала-шаға, жора-жолдас, некен-саяқ, ағыл-тегіл, әлем-жәлем, шөп-шалам* etc.

Double words are formed in the language in two different ways: 1) through the duplication of two words; 2) through the repetition of one word. In connection with this, in Kazakh linguistics, there is a division of double words into two types: 1) double words; 2) secondary double words.

Double words are very numerous in the language, they are formed from two words that are close in meaning and give a single lexical meaning. For example, *аяқ-табақ* if the double word "ыдыс" refers to the concept of, *ине-жіп* general name of the items you need to sew a case, *туған-туысқан* the double word means "туыс". Therefore, in the meaning of the double double words, accumulation, generalization is the meaning. Although the synonyms of double words are two different words, they necessarily belong to the same word class.

Redundant double words are made by repeating the same word twice. For example, *қора-қора, бау-бау, үйір-үйір, құшақ-құшақ* etc. These secondary double words do not represent the lexical meaning of their individual counterparts, they represent the size, quantity, and territory of an object. In the process of word formation, the components of double words acquired lexical meanings other than their original meanings.

In the language, repeated double words are found in different compositions. 1) reduplication in root form without suffix (*тау-тау, өркеш-өркеш* etc.); 2) one is an additional repetition (*бетпе-бет, кімде-кім, қолма-қол* etc.); 3) both are complementary repetitions (*қолдан-қолға, өзінен-өзі* etc.).

Compound words. Compound words are made up of two or more words and have a single lexical meaning. In a sentence, it answers one question and serves as one part of the sentence. It is taken ready for the sentence. Compound compound words, like other types of compound words, have a fixed composition, their parts cannot be replaced, they are pronounced with the same rhythm. Unlike other types of complex words, compound words are written together and double words

are written with a hyphen, while compound words are written separately.

There are many compound words. For example, *ауыз әдебиеті, он бес, екі жүз, жаз бойы, қара көк, қызыл күрең, келіп кет, кіріп шық, тарс етті, құрмет ет, жақсылық қыл, көмек ет* etc. Compound words are also formed from the combination of the meanings of their counterparts.

Among complex words, there is a peculiarity in the formation of complex verbs and Quranic verbs. Compound verbs are connected by a prepositional suffix, that is, a preposition serves as a connecting link between two verbs. Prepositional suffixes, which are now retained in the composition of complex verbs, distinguish complex verbs from complex words that are connected without another suffix. For example, *келіп кет, кіріп шық* etc.

Qur'anic verbs in the group of complex words also have their own characteristics from other complex words. If a complex word is formed from independent words with a full meaning, the Koranic verbs are formed from a combination (conjugation) of a noun with an independent meaning and an auxiliary verb. For example, *көмек ет, құрмет ет, қызмет қыл, телефон соқ* etc. Auxiliary verbs in the Qur'anic verbs function as suffixes that add action meaning to nouns and verbs. For example, *табыс ет – тапсыр, баян ет – баянда, мазақ қыл – мазақта, үміт ет – үміттен* etc. Just as suffixes attached to nouns add action meaning to it and turn it into a verb, auxiliary verbs also add action meaning to nouns and turn it into a verb. However, it seems that the auxiliary verbs forming the Qur'anic verbs have the same grammatical meaning as the suffixes, but in fact, this phenomenon began when the auxiliary verbs were independent words with a full meaning, and then their verb form lost its original meaning and became auxiliary. [7].

All compounds in compound words have a word-forming function. However, there is a difference in their function. For example, *алып кел, беріп кел, көріп кел, біліп кел, қызмет ет, жәрдем ет, адам ет* in all complex verbs, the first conjugation changes and the second conjugation remains constant. *Ііс май, тоң май; ауыз омыртқа, бел омыртқа; ал қызыл, қоңыр қызыл, күңгірт қызыл* also have this feature. And *он бір, он екі, он үш* in the plural nouns, one form is stable and one form is variable. If so, this phenomenon is characteristic of compound nouns. Related to this is the composition of complex words *тірек сыңар* and *ауыспалы сыңар* is divided into.

The position of the anchors in complex words is fixed, usually it is the second part of complex words. For example, *алып қайт, келіп қайт, көріп қайт, тоқпан жілік, асықты жілік, ортан жілік, қара көк, күлгін көк, ашық көк, екі мың, үш мың, бес жүз, сегіз жүз* etc. however, there are situations contrary to this principle. In the way of formation of numerals, the anchor is in the first place. For example, *он бір, он екі, он үш* etc.

Abbreviated words.

Abbreviated words occupy a large place in the language due to the regularity of shortening in the language. During the era of Soviet power, many words

shortened from the Russian language entered. For example, КПСС, партком, колхоз, совхоз, СССР, компартия etc. Words such as archaism and historicism are now added to the list of words, and shortened words are also appearing today. For example, ТМД (Тәуелсіз мемлекеттер достастығы), АлМУ (Алматы мемлекеттік университеті), ҚазҰУ (Қазақ ұлттық университеті) etc.

The difference between shortened words and other types of complex words is that shortened words retain their full meaning, that is, word formation does not create new meaning in shortened words. However, abbreviated words belong to word creation. Because abbreviated words serve as independent words as a variant of a complex full name. Meets all requirements for personal speech. Abbreviated words have a certain meaning, are ready-made words in the language, enter into a sentence as a ready-made word, answer a question in a sentence. The composition of shortened words is stable, functions as a part of a sentence, and is pronounced with one accent. Therefore, shortened words, like other types of complex words, take place as individual words from the group of lexical units in the language.

Lexical-semantic approach.

In the lexical-semantic approach, there is no change in the content of the word, the change is only in the meaning of the word. A word already existing in the language acquires a new meaning while preserving its sound composition. Since there is only a semantic change in creating a derived word, this method is called a lexical-semantic method. This method of word formation has been in our language since ancient times. For example, the adjective *ақ*, meaning color, later added the meanings "адал", "тағам атауы" (dairy food), "truth, reality".

There are many words in our language where nouns have become words through the materialization process through the lexical-semantic approach. For example: *бүлдірген, ағарған, айтыс, қоршау, ақ, жетісі, қырқы, жаратқан, туысқан* etc.

Adverbs were also formed through the aging of adverbial endings, that is, with the participation of the lexical-semantic approach. For example, *текке, бірден, зорға, бекерге, кейде, шетінен, шынымен, қапыда, етпетінен, шалқасынан* etc.

Many terms were created in our language using the lexical-semantic approach. For example, *екпін, буын, мағына, үстеу, жұрнақ* etc., which are linguistic terms. The words were initially meant for the general public and gradually acquired a term meaning. This phenomenon is characteristic of other fields of science. For example, *теңеу, суреттеу, әңгіме* әдебиет terms, *бұрыш, көбейту, қосу, алу* mathematical terms have migrated to new meanings through this lexico-semantic approach to word formation.

Thus, the examples given indicate that the lexico-semantic approach has its own place in the enrichment of vocabulary. And all derived words formed by word-forming methods are the result of the word-forming process.

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